

**DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S MENTAL EDUCATION COMPETENCIES
(IN THE EXAMPLE OF PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION)****Adilbayeva Gulsaya Yerkin kizi****2nd year student of Chirchik State Pedagogical University, Faculty of Preschool
Education**

Abstract: In this article, the necessity and methods of developing intellectual competences in children of preschool age, as well as the development of them into moral, ethical, cultural, political, legal, economic, socially mature, independent-thinking mature generations, the variety of methods that ensure the mental development of children - includes the creation of various tools, methods, and necessary conditions.

Key words: mental, spiritual, moral, economic, mature generation, method, tool, ability, mental development.

INTRODUCTION

Educating the young generation as a fully mature person is an objective necessity arising from the needs of society. Mental education is one of the most important aspects of social education. Mental education is a regular and goal-based pedagogical influence on the young generation in order to develop the mind. So, the mind in a broad sense is a set of cognitive processes that includes thinking and imagination, starting from perception and perception, and it is the knowledge, skills and abilities, standards, rules that the young generation has accumulated. and others. This situation is carried out by adults and includes the creation of various tools, methods, and necessary conditions that ensure the mental development of children. It is carried out in the process of hard work, productive activities [painting, clay). Acquiring the system of modern pedagogic knowledge, accumulating them, developing creative thinking and acquiring new knowledge are the main indicators of mental development. The task of intellectual education is determined by its content, method and organization. The results of the psychological-pedagogical research carried out in recent years show that there are great opportunities in the mental development of children in the period of preschool education. All this is necessary to further deepen and expand the scope of knowledge, qualifications and skills given to children of preschool age. By the end of preschool age, children will have a large amount of simple knowledge and understanding of the surrounding environment, they will master the basic thinking process, they will be able to distinguish between important and non-important aspects of events in objects and objects. they become aware of cause-effect relationships. The initial

indicators of educational activity are formed in them. Therefore, it is very important to develop it from the kindergarten age.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Mental education of children of preschool age is the influence of adults on the basis of a certain goal, aimed at developing the thinking activity of children. It includes giving children knowledge about the world around them, systematizing them, arousing children's interest in learning, developing mental skills and abilities, and developing cognitive abilities. The role of mental education in preparing children of preschool age for school is especially large. Because the mind is a collection of processes from feelings and perception to thinking and imagination. Mental development is manifested in the ability to generalize and see events in various connections and relationships. The mental development of children of preschool age is carried out in the process of activity, first as a result of being in contact, as a result of activities performed with objects, and then in the process of learning, work, productive activities: drawing, making things from clay and plasticine, applique, seeing - making. is increased. Education and upbringing have an effective effect on the mental development of a child.

In order to properly organize the mental education of children of preschool age, it is necessary to know the laws and possibilities of their mental development. The task of intellectual education is determined by its content, method and organization. The science of pedagogy and psychology effectively solves the tasks of mental education, on the one hand, the effective use of the child's capabilities, on the other hand, to find ways to avoid excessive exhaustion, which can cause general fatigue of the child's body, mental development of children of preschool age. studies the laws and possibilities. The results of psychological-pedagogical research conducted in recent years have shown that there are great opportunities in the mental development of children during preschool education. All this is evidence that it is desirable to deepen and expand the content of knowledge, skills and skills given to children of preschool age. By the end of preschool education, children acquire a large amount of the simplest knowledge and understanding of the environment, master the basic thought processes. Full intellectual development takes place only in the process of well-organized activity, therefore, the main task of teachers and educators is to create the necessary conditions for educational influence on the child with a specific goal in mind. The child is always among objects and events, always gets acquainted with something, learns something, touches, smells, pulls and listens to something. In this way, he gradually learns the world.

A child gathers knowledge and experience about the things around him only because of his intuition. Perception is a more complex process, it is formed on the basis of sensations, after

holding an apple in your hand, looking at it and eating it, you see it as a whole thing, at the same time round, red, fragrant, delicious. and etc. perceives. Mental education develops children's independent cognitive abilities, mental work culture, mental knowledge, skills and qualifications. Knowledge consists of the content of various sciences in the form of ideas and concepts, rules, laws, and systems. The task of mental education is to form a system of generalized knowledge of a high level that fully reflects events and phenomena in children. Knowledge is the basis of worldview. Development of mental activity depends on the size and nature of knowledge. The development of mental activity also means the formation of intuition and perception of mental processes, impression, memory, thinking, imagination and speech. Children of preschool age are introduced to social events and events that are understandable to them, people's work, national holidays, and the life of some peoples living in our republic. These events will help to arouse interest in the social life of our society, love for the Motherland and form the foundations of internationalism. Mental education consists of regularly and systematically developing the cognitive abilities of children of preschool age, equipping them with the simplest system of knowledge defined in the kindergarten program, and forming skills and abilities. Education plays a leading role in mental education of children of preschool age. Because all issues related to intellectual education are solved during the educational process. Education implies consistently providing knowledge to children, identifying and systematizing this knowledge, developing cognitive processes and thinking activity.

Education helps to develop qualities such as observation, curiosity and thoroughness, intelligence, criticality. In the process of education, the basics of educational activities are formed in children, important conditions are created for them to study successfully at school.

CONCLUSION

Life requires education in two different ways. The first way is for children to acquire knowledge and skills through interaction with adults. This is determined by behavior, labor activity, and so on. But the knowledge and skills acquired in this way do not give the child the opportunity to participate independently in various areas of life. The second way of education is the systematic arming of children with the necessary knowledge, skills and abilities by specially trained people in special educational institutions. The purpose of education in this way is to acquaint the young generation with the scientific achievements necessary for modern production, active participation in the socio-political and cultural life of society. All scholars, poets and writers gained respect and attention by studying in prestigious educational institutions of their time.

Abu Nasr Farabi, Mahmud Koshgari, Abu Raikhan Beruni, Abdurakhman Jami, Mirza Ulugbek, Alisher Navoi, Ibn Sina, Abu Abdullah Rudaki, Abu Saidrasul Azizi, Muhammad Sharif Sufizada, Abdul Qadir Shakiri, Abdulla Avloni and others have mastered all aspects of science by acquiring perfect knowledge. who made great discoveries and innovations in their fields, and at the same time called others to acquire knowledge.

List of used literature:

1. Mirziyoyev SH.M Tanqidiy tahlil, qat'iy tartib-intizom va shaxsiy javobgarlik – har bir rahbar faoliyatining kundalik qoidasi bo'lishi kerak.-T., «O'zbekiston», 2017.-104 b.
2. Mirziyoyev SH.M “Milliy tarqqiyot yo'limizni qatiyat bilan davom ettirib yangi bosqichga ko'taramiz”-O'zbekiston 2017y. 312 b.
3. Xasanboyeva.O.U.va boshqalar. “Maktabgacha ta'lim pedagogikasi”.T., «Ilm ziyo» 2006 y.
4. Sh.A.Sodiqova “Maktabgacha pedagogika”. “Tafakkur sarchashmalari” T.: 2013 y.
5. N.M.Kayumova “Maktabgacha pedagogika”. “TDPU” nashriyoti T.: 2013 y.
6. Xasanboyev J.Y. va boshqalar. Pedagogika. O'quv qo'llanma.- T., “Fan”.2006 y.